

PEDAGOGICAL OPPORTUNITIES AND IMPORTANCE OF LEARNING FOREIGN LANGUAGES IN UZBEKISTAN

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Abstract: This article discusses the opportunities, measures, new reforms and achievements made in the education system in our country in learning foreign languages, as well as the role of foreign languages in the lives of citizens of Uzbekistan and the advantages of learning a foreign language.

Keywords: foreign languages, reforms, efficiency, modern technologies, language exchange, curricula.

Introduction.

Language learning is one of the most important areas in human society. In this era of comprehensive development, especially in countries like Uzbekistan, where globalization and international cooperation are rapidly influencing society and economy, it is no exaggeration to say that communication in foreign languages has become a tradition. The government and citizens of Uzbekistan pay great attention to learning foreign languages, in which English, Russian and other world languages take the main place. Also, foreign languages play a significant role in the lives of citizens of Uzbekistan, that is, they are considered an important factor in everything from education to employment. The reason for this is that the government, recognizing its importance in forming a competitive, globally developed workforce, has set foreign language teaching as a priority. The government considers this to be effective for Uzbekistan and every citizen living in it. Currently, living in a rapidly developing era, it is impossible not to learn a foreign language.

In addition, modern educational programs are widely used, combining traditional classroom teaching with modern technologies. Schools and educational institutions include multimedia resources, online assignments, and video conferencing to improve language skills. However, learning a foreign language opens up many opportunities. Our esteemed President Shavkat Mirziyoyev is creating new opportunities for every young generation who wants to get an education and extending a helping hand to them. It should be noted that government-sponsored programs such as the President's Schools, the El-Yurt Umidi Foundation, and advanced language programs have provided access to scholarships and advanced language programs. These initiatives are being implemented to promote the interest of each young generation in social

education. The new Uzbekistan will certainly support and encourage creative, ambitious young people who know a foreign language. What is required of us is that we, the youth, must contribute to the development of our profession as specialists in our field and to the development of the youth after us as superior personnel. For this, many conditions are being created in our country. Educational programs abroad, exchange opportunities, and virtual language exchange have become open to many Uzbek students. Such deep experiences are considered very effective in fostering cultural understanding. These include educational institutions that Uzbekistan is creating in cooperation with foreign countries.

It is not for nothing that prestigious higher education institutions are considered major centers of science today. Currently, new higher education institutions are being established, branches of leading universities in the world. Also, non-state higher education institutions are being established on the basis of a public-private partnership system. All this helps to improve the quality of education. In the development of the new Uzbekistan, new laws are being approved in order to improve the education system. For example, in April 2019, the President of Uzbekistan approved the Concept for the Development of the Public Education System by 2030. In addition to raising the level of educational infrastructure, expanding it, and improving teaching methodologies, the concept set the goal of Uzbekistan becoming one of the 30 leading countries in the world by 2030 according to the international study of assessing student achievement - PISA. The benefits of learning a foreign language are not only material, but also help to improve cognitive abilities. According to research, learning a second language plays a huge role in solving memory problems. This helps to keep the brain active and healthy. As for other advantages, many employers give preference to candidates who know two or more languages. Knowing another language can also set you apart from others. In addition, language is deeply connected to culture, which means that learning a foreign language allows you to better understand the values and traditions of another country. Mastering a foreign language is not only about fluency, it also broadens your worldview. Charlemagne, the king of the Franks, said a meaningful phrase about language: "To have another language is to have a second soul."

At a time when the distances between culture and values, concepts of national identity are shrinking day by day, the language factor plays an important and fundamental role in the integration of our youth into the world. Young people who do not know foreign languages have long understood that

there is no place for them in international business, science, politics, economics or information and communication networks. It is certainly gratifying that in Uzbekistan, young people can communicate freely in foreign languages. All adolescents show a special interest in learning a foreign language. Effective work is also being done in schools for this, and I must say that the demand for English in particular is increasing day by day. The results are closely related to the attention paid to high-level teaching of foreign languages at all stages of the continuous education system and the creation of conditions for young people. There are factors that influence young people's ability to learn foreign languages, for example, regardless of the direction they choose, if they have at least a B2 level language certificate in a foreign language when entering a university, they are given 100 percent of the foreign language exam score. This creates an opportunity for them to prepare better than other subjects and prepare for and receive a certificate in that subject as well.

The fact that the state compensates young people who score 7.0 or higher in internationally recognized language proficiency exams such as IELTS for their exam fees is a clear example of the attention and opportunity for young people to learn foreign languages. The intended goal is to discover young people who are knowledgeable in language skills and prepare highly educated personnel who are competitive in the global market.

Not only young people, but also adults are taking advantage of these opportunities. A center for teaching citizens in foreign languages and targeted training for work in foreign countries will be established in Uzbekistan. Within the framework of training courses, students will be trained in English, German, Japanese, Korean, Arabic and other foreign languages in high demand on a paid-contract basis. Accordingly, on April 17, a Government Resolution [No. 213] "On measures to improve the system of training young people in professions (specialties) and foreign languages" was adopted. The Ministry of Justice reported this. According to it, a center for teaching citizens in foreign languages and targeted training for work in foreign countries will be established. In the event that students who are involved in vocational education institutions independently study a foreign language and present an international or equivalent certificate, 50 percent of the expenses incurred by the student for studying a foreign language or a part not exceeding 10 times the basic calculation amount will be reimbursed from the State Budget. In the new Uzbekistan, full opportunities are being created for the education of young people. Learning a foreign language can be useful not only for the individual, but

such personnel are necessary for Uzbekistan.

Our President emphasized at the 72nd session of the UN General Assembly that “The future and well-being of our planet depend on what kind of people our children will become. Our main task is to create the necessary conditions for young people to realize their potential.” Therefore, we young people should not stop learning, because knowledge is a lamp that guides us on a bright path.

Conclusion.

In conclusion, it should be noted that in today's era of globalization, it is important to have any second language. Every person who knows a foreign language, especially young people, should make their contribution to the prosperity of our country, especially if they use it effectively. Of course, this also plays an important role in building the career of every person who knows a foreign language. We need to make the most of the opportunities created for young people and try our best to raise New Uzbekistan to great heights and take a place among the countries with high ratings in the world in terms of education. It is no exaggeration to say that every young person who studies science should strive forward with this motto of our President. "Salvation is in education, salvation is in upbringing, salvation is in knowledge. Because all noble goals are achieved through knowledge and upbringing." Let us make the most of the opportunity given to us, time is the supreme judge, and let us spend our time on useful things.

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